

Research Article

Smart Car Key (KeyBuddy)

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Abstract: *This paper introduces "Keybuddy," a smart car key that makes it simple for people to locate lost keys. It makes use of a sound alert system that links to a smartphone app and GPS tracking. These features allow users to find their keys on a map or set them to beep when they are close by. Keybuddy is particularly useful for frequent travellers, busy parents, and forgetful people. The goal of this innovation is to make daily life safer and easier by collaborating with Perodua, the leading automaker in Malaysia. It is a clever and sustainable solution for modern living since it also helps lower stress, save time, and reduce waste from replacing misplaced keys.*

Keywords: *car key, GPS tracking, Bluetooth, misplaced, forgetful, Keybuddy, Perodua*

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1. INTRODUCTION

It can be a surprisingly upsetting experience to lose common items in today's world, where time is valuable and convenience is highly valued. Car key loss is among the most common and particularly annoying situations. Losing your car keys can cause delays, stress, and wasteful time spent looking for them, whether you are driving to an important meeting, trying to get to work on time, or just running errands. This issue is becoming more widespread as people get more involved and distracted by the responsibilities of everyday life.

Realizing this, the smart car key with sound emitting and GPS tracking features provides a creative and incredibly useful solution. By combining latest smart features, this innovative technology makes it easier for users to deal with this common problem by rapidly locating their misplaced car keys. Through a smartphone app, the user can use GPS tracking to locate their key accurately on a map, and the sound-emitting feature enables them to activate a beep, which helps them locate the key even if it is hidden in a hard-to-reach place, under furniture, or inside a bag. Combining modern technology and convenience not only makes it easier to find keys, but it also has the potential to improve people's quality of life in any situations.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The smart car key innovation for forgetful individuals uses tracking and reminder technology to make it easier for them to find their keys. Because this type of key has a built-in Bluetooth or GPS, users can locate it with the aid of a smartphone application. If the key is misplaced, users can use the smartphone app to see its last known location or click to hear a notification, which will make it easier to find the key by vibrating or ringing. This innovation aims to lessen the stress related to key management, particularly for those who misplace their keys frequently.

The GPS tracking feature of the car key allows users to track the exact location of their keys using a smartphone app. If you activate the sound-emitting feature, the key will beep loudly and clearly or sound an alert if it is within a certain range. This enables users to easily locate their keys, regardless of whether they are buried deep within a bag, buried under furniture, or lying in an unexpected place. The user's smartphone app and the key combine. By displaying the key's current location on a map through the GPS tracking system, users can quickly find and navigate to it. To make finding the key even simpler, the app can also have it make a sound if it is close by (for example, inside the house or car).

For this innovation of smart car key or Keybuddy to be successful, it will have a collaboration with Perodua as it is Malaysia largest car manufacturer. Perodua is also a familiar name for all people and most people use a car from Perodua. Perodua is a trusted company that focuses on the quality of its products. Perodua also offer products and services towards their customer's needs and wants. This can also ease us because Perodua already have the ability to create advance product and having a wide knowledge about the relationship of a car and its key.

3. FINDINGS

Keybuddy, a smart car key that addresses the prevalent problem of misplacing car keys. Using a smartphone app, it locates lost keys quickly by using GPS tracking and a sound-emitting feature. Keybuddy provides time-saving features, convenience, and security to busy parents, frequent travellers, and forgetful people. It is suggested that the product work with Perodua, the top automaker in Malaysia, to guarantee accessibility and quality. In addition to improving security and lowering stress, Keybuddy supports environmental sustainability by lowering the need to replace misplaced keys, which frequently results in waste. This innovative tool simplifies daily tasks and improves the effectiveness of car key management.

3.1 *Its purpose (WHY)*

The smart car key innovation's main goal is to make it easier for people to find their keys and avoid accidental misplacement. This will help to increase ease and peace of mind. Individuals who frequently lose their keys or leave them in different places will find this innovation really helpful. Smart car keys improve key management by combining tracking and sound or notification features, which reduces the stress and time lost in finding the car key.

By having this smart car key or Keybuddy, it will help to reduce the risk of having stress. It is because it will eliminate all the struggle in remembering or finding your car key that has been misplace. Using smart car key, the car owner just needs to open the app in their smartphone that linked to the smart car key and look at the location of the key or the car owner can click a button in that app to make the key vibrate or make a sound. With this, the car owner can easily find the key that

have been misplaced by themselves. The users will also have a peace of mind and do not need to worry a lot when they misplace or forget where they put their car key.

Furthermore, this innovation of smart car key can also enhance the security and safety of the car owner. As we know, the smart car key will have a built-in Bluetooth and GPS, so these two features will really be beneficial to the user. For example, if the user does not remember where they put their car key and misplaces it when they are outside of their home, the car key might have been stolen or found by the wrong person. So, with this smart car key, the car owner's safety is secure as we can know where the car key is. This can also be applied if your car was stolen and you need to know the location, you just need to open the app that is linked to the smart car key in your smartphone and know the location. So, you can easily make a report to the police about your stolen car and give the details about the location.

As we can see, the smart car key or Keybuddy innovation has many purposes in our daily life. This innovation of smart car key offers numerous benefits for us like the safety and the convenience of using it. Smart car key simplifies the life of people who constantly forget where they put their car key. Innovation of smart car key or Keybuddy is really a progress for future lifestyle and a step forward in making a car owner's life easier, safer and more efficient.

3.2. The issues that the social innovation was trying to address (WHAT)

One of the most common issues that smart car key or Keybuddy was trying to address is losing or misplacing car keys. Some people frequently lose track of where they put their keys, whether it is at home, in their luggage, or even at their friend's house. Looking for lost keys can be a waste of time and an unnecessary source of stress, especially when you are rushed in time. This can lead to stress and mood swings for the car owner. When you are in a rush, you will not think right and cannot even remember where you put your car key. Finding the key can also be hard as you feel stress about it.

In addition, when using a normal key and you lose it, you need to make a new key, duplicate or replace it and it will cost you a lot. Besides being expensive, it is also time-consuming as you need to wait for your key to be ordered from the dealership or for the duplicate key. By having a smart car key, you do not need to be worried about losing your car key anymore. This will help you to save more time instead of spending more hours just searching for the lost key. Plus, a smart car key will also save you some money as your car key will not be lost forever anymore.

The next issue is there is no tracking for a lost key but with this innovation of smart car key or Keybuddy, you do not need to be worried anymore because a smart car key comes with built-in GPS so that you can easily track your car key location if you misplace it. Before this, it will be really frustrating to search for the normal key as it is small and does not have any features except a button for lock and open a car. But now with a smart car key or Keybuddy, you can just open the app on your smartphone that is linked with the key and search the location of the key. You can easily find it without any stress or struggle.

The next issue is the worst thing that can happen when you misplace your car key is it can be stolen. When you are going out and you misplace your car key or the key falls from your bag or pocket, there is a big chance that it can be stolen or found by the wrong person. When this happens, those people who found your key can steal your car and run away with it. But, by having a smart car key, you do not need to be worried anymore because you can locate your car key or you can click a

button in the app so the key will make sound like ringing or beeping. This will reduce the risk of the car key to be stolen easily.

3.3. The users of the innovation (WHO)

a. Forgetful and Disorganized person

Car key misplacement or forgetfulness is one of the main problems that the smart car key innovation attempts to solve. Due to busy schedules, distractions, or just the human tendency to lose things, forgetfulness is a common issue for many people. For these people, regular car keys can be an ongoing reason of stress. For those who frequently lose things or forget where they put their car keys, the smart key system offers a convenient solution. They do not have to worry about the stress of a misplaced key or have to go back and forth to find the key. So, people can stop wasting time looking through their pockets or bags to see where they put their keys.

b. Parents

The lives of parents are hectic and often chaotic, especially for those with small children. Parents may have to handle several tasks at once in order to manage school runs, extracurricular activities, grocery shopping, and other daily responsibilities. Under such conditions, it can be extremely difficult to find or handle standard car keys while handling kids, luggage, or shopping carts. When we are handling too many things at one time, sometimes we tend to become careless so it is not impossible for us to drop our car key without realizing that. Another scenarios are when parents are at home with their children especially the little one, they tend to play with the small object like the car key. So, it is also not impossible for the car key to be lost.

c. Frequent traveller

The smart car key provides incomparable flexibility and ease for people who travel frequently, such as business travellers or those who take road trips on a regular basis. Normal car keys are prone to being misplaced or forgotten while traveling, which can cause serious problems. In the case of car sharing services for traveller which often several people need access to same vehicle but at a different time. Most of the time, case like misplacing the car key or forgot where they put the car key will always happen. It is because they used a same car but only on different time and different people. So, when they car key always move around passing from one person to another, it has a high chance to be lost. But, when using smart car key or Keybuddy, they do not need to be worried anymore as the key will be easily found using only one app in their smartphone.

4. DISCUSSION

The Keybuddy is a smart car key designed to solve the common problem of losing car keys. With GPS tracking and a sound-emitting feature, users can easily find their keys using a smartphone app. These features save time, reduce stress, and improve convenience. The product is especially useful for forgetful individuals, busy parents, and frequent travellers. A collaboration with Perodua, Malaysia's largest car manufacturer, would ensure the Keybuddy reaches a wider audience and works well with popular car models. Besides convenience, the Keybuddy enhances security by preventing lost keys from being misused. It also supports environmental sustainability by reducing the need for replacements, which often contribute to waste. In conclusion, the Keybuddy is a practical and innovative solution that simplifies key management, improves daily life, and addresses security and environmental concerns.

5. CONCLUSION

The ability of the smart car key to reduce the stress and frustration that frequently accompany misplacing car keys is its main significance. Many people frequently lose their keys, and looking for them can be frustrating and time consuming. While the sound feature enables users to activate an audible beep from the key when it is in close range, the GPS tracking feature enables users to locate the key quickly using an app on their smartphone. This reduces the need for people to spend time searching through rooms, bags, or drawers in an attempt to find a misplaced key.

Apart from being convenient, the smart car key also provides an extra degree of protection. Normal keys can be misplaced or duplicated, which creates a risk if they end up in the wrong hands. An additional advantage of a smart key with GPS tracking is that it makes it easier for users to find their keys and makes sure they are never left in risky or dangerous areas. In the event that the key is lost in public, the user can locate it and instantly get it back before it is permanently lost. This will keep the society safe and secure.

Although helping users find lost keys is the main purpose of the smart car key, there are also unforeseen environmental advantages. Normal key fobs contribute to waste because they are frequently made of plastic and are lost or replaced. Multiple physical keys or key fobs are not necessary when a smart key that connects to a smartphone or a single digital fob is used.

In conclusion, the Keybuddy is an innovative smart car key that solves the common issue of misplaced keys. With GPS tracking, a sound-emitting feature, and smartphone integration, it offers convenience, security, and environmental benefits. This product simplifies daily life and enhances safety, making it a valuable tool for modern living.

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